

The Polemical And Contradictory Morphological Problems Of The Son Of A Bird In The Book Of The Key

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
August 03, 2021

Accepted:
March 06, 2022

Keywords :

Son Of A Bird, Illness,
Argument, Contradiction

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.6332905

Abstract

Reasoning is an important aspect of scientific research in various fields of science. It is also a prominent manifestation of protest. Linguists have relied on it to strengthen their judgments, strengthen their protests, and answer all the questions that can be raised in the learner's mind about the origin of setting limits to this language. Why was this provision for this phenomenon the only other provision?. One scholar who was interested in writing in general, and the Algebra in particular, is Imam Ibn Asfour al-Ashbili. The research deals with the study of the controversial and contradictory ills of Ibn Asfour (T:669H), which are broadcast in a psychological book from Arabic books; Because of the banking detectors, as well as the close connection between these detectors and the banking cause, the researcher selectively chose the son of a bird's disease. The search included two requests: The book was criticized by Ibn Asfour for his criticisms of the Foreign Exchange Scholars. Most of his ailments were deep, searching for the mysteries of the language and relying on imagined debate. Conflicting banking problems, showing the ills in which Ibn Asfour contradicted himself, whether this contradiction was found in his book, the key, or in his other works; Because he has approved in it the agreed-upon reasoning of scientists that he has rejected, or has not recognized in (his key), and I have dealt with the reasoning beside him: At the beginning of each episode I present the poetry home for which the illness was performed, and I complete the poetry house if what Ibn Asfour sang is part, chest, or disability. I mention the different stories of the house, and I discuss these problems with former and later Arab scholars.

Introduction

These are all things that are bad after educational and standard ills. They supplement previous ones, and they are called "the cause of the illness", and they are called "fictional ills" (Aziza Fawal, 1992): 683). It is an answer to probabilistic questions about grammatical or banking issues, justifying the methods of pregnancy and the similarities referred to. Ibn Asfour used the method of argument and argument in many of his banking matters; To strengthen his opinion and point of view in devising the analogy and establishing the evidence, or to issue a verdict that introduces a rule for a banking issue, for example, so that he feels his inquiries about this issue, or what probability (hypothetical) questions may be asked about it, by saying: If one says:... The answer is:...Because...If you say... So the answer...An example of the controversial illness of a bird's son is:

First: The controversial issue in a passport may be (oleg) at the weight of (verb) or (verb)

The son of Asfour mentioned his dialectical ailment, while he explained it in the words of the poet: 453) a pole from Damascus came and threw it

Ibn Asfour came to him, citing the weight of (oleg): Indeed, a whisper is original and there is no substitute for "W." Scholars differ in the weight of (W) over three sayings:

The first one: Sibwe went on to say that his weight (action) and his shock were original. It is (q) the word, and the wow is superfluous. "This loyalty and intimacy are increased more in the daughters of three; they are superfluous until a matter comes up between (Ulak), for (Olqa) the increase is greater; He tells you: A man is divorced, and he is habitual. Had it not been proved (I do); 'Cause I do more of this beating than Sibwe did, 1988: 3/195). This is to say that if it were not for the problem of making the (Hamzah) original, the increase would have been more than the (Wau) increase; Because the build (I do) in this multiplication is more measured than build (and do). He continued it at that time, and the cooler: 3/316).

Second saying: Al-Kasai said that according to the weight of (I do), the Wa is original, and the Hamza is superfluous. The glass, the son of a jinn, the son of a throne, and the son of a bird, with various increments, do not affect the meaning of the main text. Al-Kasai said: I do. Marwan said: "I felt ashamed for you, O Sheik." (The Glass, 1983: 194).

Third: Abu Ali Al-Farsi went so far as to say, "Olga" is as big as Foal. He said, "I am not. "Oleg bears two types of weight, one of which is: If you call him a man for this description, he may be (more) a person who is worthy of divorce, if he hastens. One of them is the reading of Our Lady Aisha - may Allah be pleased with her and her father - Ibn Abbas, Isa, Ibn Aumar and Zayd ibn Ali: (giving it in your tongue) (Son of Genie, 1999: 2/104), he said:

a pole from Damascus came and threw it

He is as such (as I do), and the jigsaw is an extra, and the F. If a man is called by him for this he will not be dismissed." (Abu Ali Al-Farsi, 554:1999). And (receive) at home its origin: (Toulaq) Wau was deleted; Because it is located between a spring and a fraction, this indicates that the Wau are original and that the Nile is followed by the two-sided leave. Oleg may increase his shaking, and she is the first one with the (Nile, 1419: 4/563). He understands from this that Ali's father and his follower authorized him to (do); Because it's from the pollock, which is the velocity. 4/1447), and added to it a meaning other than its first meaning, which is (insanity). He agreed with Al-Qulin the son of Jeni, Al-Jawahiri, Al-Zamkhashri, the son of Jesun, the son of Berri, Al-Akbari, the son of Yaish, and Rukn Al-Din (Al-Zakhshari, 1993): 501. The son of Asfour mentioned on Jadaliyya, in its reply, which are in the first place hard-working reasons justifying the Persian's passage of two things at the height of weight (Ulak). "If it is said: Arabs say: The man threw up, and if it were as he had stated, they would have said: He replied: They swapped the whisper first; For joining it is a necessary attachment, as they said in (Waad): (Prepare) for that. So it says: If the whisper was in Luke instead of Wau they would say: (luke) and (luke), as they said: (Repeat) and (promise). The answer: that he had this as a necessary allowance, as they said in the plural of (pagan): He is a pagan, but they did not utter it at all... As they said to the man: To drop it in the water, Rags said (Al-Qaisi, 1987): 2/890:(

Oleg Fi Kasbah al-Adafa

They did not say: (Duff), and that was the origin; Because as Ibn Al-A'arabi and other people of the language claim, 'I will not pay the lip if it drops'. but they made him beat her instead of wasting; Because of the clarity of the derivative, the lack of material (and lug), and their obligation to substitute (lesser), they said: (familiar), and they did not say: Moloug, they returned to the Wau and still had a heartache. So it says: This kind of allowance is a little bit necessary. The answer: But if the original of a whisper also falls first into a small proverb, then there are few words coming from it, and therefore both things are rewarded for it. Ibn Asfour, 2015: 2/625)

The son of Asfour refused to accept the two sides' justifications for the weight of (Ulak), and the Persian reasoned the dialectic; He didn't take it; For he did not come in hearing (and saying), nor in the derivation (or saying) of the Wau, in explanation of this: "It is true that I have an original whisper; Because if necessary, the allowance may be returned to it at some point, don't you see that they said: "Wathiq" and "Aouthiq", as well as "Al-Baria", are among those most committed to mitigation. However, Arabs have shown the trauma that is the root of what they said: God cleared the creations, and so there is every necessary substitute if they settle down. I mean that the original must appear somewhere, and we have not heard them utter a wau in any of the (Ulak) manners intended for madness, but they say: (oleg), (alak), and (ilk) in a sense, and they said to the prayer: (cat) They said: Let him be thrown down by God. A man who is familiar and charming. This shows that whispers are an original and irreplaceable thing." (Ibn Asfour, 2015: 2/626)

After reviewing the sayings of scholars, it seems to me that Sibuyeh and Ibn Asfour went so far as to say that he did and that his original weight and shock was more likely, for the following reasons

Number one: He did not hear about Arabs (Molouk) in the sense of madness, but only found (Muawwk), and if (I do) a measurement more than (I do), we would explain this by making the argument that (Hamzah) is the origin, from its appearance in the name of the effect which is derived from (Less), it is (Muawwk)

Number two: It is permissible to have (oligarchs) at the weight of (more) than (less); Because it is proven that the Wo is authentic, so the Wo must have an original, so its origin must be (and indeed it must be); And for the Wayne meeting, I replaced the first Wayu with a murmur (glass, 1971: 15)

Number three: The whisper appeared in the object's name, which was "friendly," though it had a slight effect: "Molouk", K (Promised) (Nelly, 1419: 4/564.(

Fourth: That the quirk appeared in the derivative, and carrying what is known as the first derivative of the pregnancy over what was not known to him, is a means of knowing the original letters of the appendix, as it is based on flipping his different faces. This process has a great impact on knowing the authenticity of the letters, or not.

Second: The dialectical problem of increasing the whisper in the waiter.

Also of this ailment is what the son of a bird did in the words of the poet (Ibn Berri, 1985: 623:(

He's got a nylon at night

The son of a bird came to him, explaining that the Nideles, who are the nightmare, are the ones who have been defeated. Nidal has an exaggerated charm, and scholars have differed in the interpretation of this word and the reasoning behind its doctrine, as follows:

The first one: Abu Ali Al-Farsi thought the hump in Nideles was too great a nightmare; For two reasons:

First problem: They said, in the sense of nylon; Because it weighed on the weight of (Vialan) b (J) and included the Dale without a whisper, dropping the charm in that was evidence of its increase; Because it was not an addition. It is the family of Abu Ali al-Farsi, followed by Ibn Janni, Al-Thaini, Abdul Qahir al-Jurjani, Ibn Jaoun, Abu al-Barakat al-Anbari, Ibn Barri, Al-Qaisi, Abu Al-Qa'ibri, and Ibn Yaish. 241. The son of a bird agreed with them in this ailment and added a second illness to it; To explain the first, he reasoned: "They said in 'The Bartender', which is the nightmare: Nidlan, you had to make the jigsaw over, and the nylon over; In order for the origins to be united as the meaning is united, for if the whisper were to be made in the first place, the waiter would be a quaternary, and the nideles a triplet, and entry would be required in the gate of the tribe and the tribe, and that is a little bit" (Ibn Asfour, 2015: 2/629). He was also followed by Radi, Nazir al-Jaysh, and Shatbi (Radi, 1975: 2/333). Ibn Asfour then mentioned on the basis of argument, in its contents, to prove what the Persian had reasoned from the fact that the whisper was superfluous, unlike the original. Ibn Asfour stated in explanation: "If it is said: There is also little increase in the number of defeats. If there is little to be done, authenticity is first. The answer: That the increase in whispering is not the first time it is wider to him than the doors of (Sabat) and (Sabtar)..." (Ibn Asfour, 2015: 2/629.)

Second problem: It's a derivative of the I-I-I, if I cover it, and it's called the Handkerchief, and it's activated. I gathered it and gathered it, and it is the occasion of the son of Jahion, and Al-Qaisi (Ibn Jahion, 2008: 1526), and Anshid (Ashi Hamdan, 1983: 90):

We stay the money we stay the foxes

The son of a bird followed him in this suit, saying: "...- also - 'waitress' is derived from the waitress of an object, if it is covered, and from it a handkerchief, or from a waitress in a sense collected and incorporated" (Ibn Asfour, 2015 2/360). Then I sang the advanced house. He was followed by those who came after him: Rukn Al-Din Al-Asterabi (Rukn Al-Din, 2004): 2/581-582.(

Third problem: It's the sense of a waiter taking after the object (Akbari, 1995: 2/242). And so we see multiple scientists' reasons for proving that they're increasing.

Second saying: Ibn Janni also took the argument that the whisper in Naadlan was superfluous: "They also increased it in his statement: 'It is Nideles.' This is Abu Ali's speech." (Ibn Janni, 2000 : 1/124). Abu Ali Al-Farsi stated, in explanation of this, that Ibn Sayyidah, Ibn Sa'un, Ibn Barri, and Ibn Asfour quoted him as saying: "Abu Ali said: It is mentioned that Abu Amr Al-Shaibani said, "The Nidlan said, 'Break the Law, make it idolatry, and that is bad; because the word does, and we did not know this weight in their words, but the translators; It has come with a thousand and a half, so it is not right to make Nidlan attached to it; Because it's unparalleled, and it can be said: From Nideles; Because Deuteronomy is based on what is not in one as (two), (two), and (two), and as (the translators) came up with an increase similar to that of Deuteronomy, and this strengthens the saying of the Asha (the Asha): 53:(

And what will bring me to the temple? He built it, and crucified it, and became

but this is the genealogical environment, and Ibli: Pastor, as well as Hebeli" (Son of his master, 1996: 1/496). The son of Asfour followed him, and he did so differently from the illness mentioned by the scholars, saying: "The waiter to which the gold is intended was originally shaken, as there was no evidence of its increase, and if the explanation (waitresses) instead of nylon had been fixed, it would have been more worthy and more creative; to agree with Nideles in the picture and meaning; Because "Al-Naidal" in the sense of the nightmare is only known from the words of Abi Ali, and perhaps a change that took place in the book, the one Abu Al-Fattah related about it is "Al-Naidlan"... he said in the secret of Al-Sina'ah and also increased it in "Al-Naidlan"... (Ibn Asfour, 2015) : 2/630.(

After presenting the words of the scholars and their reasons for them, it seems to me that what Al-Farsi went to and said in them, that they (Al-Naadlan) opened the arts in the most successful manner; For the following reasons:

Number one: That what the son of a bird did in making Nideles more worthy of Nideles; Because the nadeel in the sense of the nightmare is not known except by what the Persian said; Because Ibn Khalawya spoke (Al-Naidal) in the sense of a nightmare, and Al-Farsi was not the first to say this in this sense; Al-Azhar also said (Al-Azhar, 2001) : 14/88.(

Number two: That the Persian malady in the novel by Abu Amr Al-Shaibani and his saying, "The Nidlan", by breaking the madness that deuteronomy is based on what is not in one, is considered; Because the son of Khalwiah said, "The waiter and the waiter opened the law and broke it and joined the judge (Ibn Khalwiyah, 1979: 87). It did not need this cost.

Number three: The form of the nylon is very heavy and involves a lot of difficulty in pronunciation; For it is not only an exit from the breaking to the annexation, but also an exit from the breaking and from the fitness to the annexation. This has added to the heavy one another, and it is the omission. Had this exit from the annexation to the breaking, it would have been lighter; Because if it starts with the lightest and then the heaviest, the cost is heavier than starting with the heaviest and then the lightest (Ibn Yaish, 2001 4/309.(

Fourth: He is one of the weights that have not been proven to have any equivalent in Arab words. For this reason, Sibwah has not proved anything of it in his building (Ibn Asfour, 2015 : 2/633.(

I noticed that Ibn Asfour adopted the method of argument and dialog by asking questions that come to mind, and he answers them. He is thus the questioner and the respondent, as his method of protest is accompanied by explanations for each of the judgments. This is evidence that the late scholars are influenced by the doctrinal sciences, speech sciences, philosophy and logic. This method of presenting opinions has led to a lot of reasoning among them, so that no matter passed without explanation.

Second requirement: Contrasting morphological problems.

Ibn Asfour was not correct in his attempt to explain all the banking rulings in his book, as he was forced to violate the ills of scholars in some of them. He then returned to appease these ills, which he rejected, and this caused him a major contradiction in his reasoning, whether this contradiction was found in different parts of his book (The Key), or in his other writings; Because he has approved in it the agreed-upon ailments of scientists that he has rejected, or has not recognized in (his key).

First: The reason for attaching the feminine h to the miniaturization of the excess female by three characters.

The son of a bird reasoned with it what the poet sang (Alqemat Al-Fahl, 1969: 73):

And I've got a lot of traveling driving Old Gemini Day Poisoned

A bird's son came to him, confirming the authenticity of his statement that they had reduced the abnormality of some of the more than three-letter female. They said, in miniature (old): (ancient), in (behind): (and a lung), even if they exceed three characters, this is out of measure; For the feminine, when it is on (four) characters and above, is the miniaturization without an air, toward their saying in (scorpion): (scorpion). If the name was trilateral, I would have reinstated it in its miniature; Because miniaturization brings something back to its origin, toward: sun, sun, and sun, although the fourth name was not intended; for its many letters, about: Zainab, Zainab, and the Ta'ee was limited to the trio; For the few of his letters (Abul Barakat al-Anbari, 1999 : 255). Quaternary also followed suit; An alert to the original, which was feminization, as you increased in the triple, but they extrapolated the T as the number of letters increased, as if the fourth letter had become its replacement (Sibwe, 1988: 3/481).

And what the T proved which is more than three letters, about: (ancient), (intimate), and (amiah), miniature: (Qadam), (Behind), and (Imam). Arab scholars have disagreed on the cause of female circumcision, and this difference was divided into three reasons, as follows:

First problem: The fur argued that the feminization of miniaturization of these conditions was the case; Because what can be mentioned and feminized when it is small, who gives his right, is the weak; Confirming and indicating his femininity, a fox followed him, as the fur said in explanation: "And all the subjects that grammaticians call: Circumstances, traits, and shops (favorite Bin Salama: 335) are male, except when I saw something female in it, except that they are feminine in front, in front, and behind. They say: So the woman and the leaf of the wall, according to the weight (and the hairy) of the wall, enter into her contemptuous fury, for this is evidence of her femininity, as well as (before): Back and forth, the poet said (Qatami, 2001:44):

Old experimentation and the dream that I I see the mistakes of living before experiences

And in front of her contempt: illiterate, illiterate"(fur: 98). He was followed in this family by Abu Bakr al-Anbari, Ibn al-Shajri, and Abu al-Barakat al-Anbari (Abu Bakr al-Anbari, 1981: 1/87). Abu Hatem denied this, saying that he does not trust his story; For he knew therein only the reminder (Abu Hatem Al-Sijastani, 1997: 211). Abu Bakr al-Anbari reasoned that if a woman were younger, he would be caught in the act of feminization; He made a distinction between his own language and that of a male. In (front of) his mention, he said in miniaturization: (ancient), and of her womanhood he said in her small: (Old), explaining his argument in its content the malfunction of causing triple female miniaturization, he reasoned: "If one says: How may the arm and the arm be smaller by the air than the females; they are of the four females, but the four females shall not the air enter into it? He was told: The problem with this is that, had they made them small, they would have made them unwitting; To put this on in the language of those who remember them, and to make it plain to them; There is a difference between the language of the feminine and the male. This is the Fur Doctrine and Abu Abbas" (Abu Bakr al-Anbari, 1981: 2/309). The problem with increasing feminization is the minimization and feminization of what can be mentioned; Fear of being clothed with the male by the female.

The son of a bird did not approve of the fur and fox, describing it as false, saying: "And this is what they have gone to, by no means measured, and not hasty in hearing: Its nullity in measurement, however, is not to be confused if it is not to be minimized and feminized, since there may be a difference between the two from other sources, such as news, signal and conscience. As for his nonchalance, he has only heard these anomalous words, and his equivalents have not heard of the names. Do you not see that no one has spoken in miniaturization (tongue) and (veil): Is it not Lysina or Howayjbah or any other person like her who is mentioned and feminine? It has been proven that this came out of its wake" (Ibn Asfour, 2015: 1/86).

Second problem: Abu Hatem Al-Sijastani said that the problem is that she is not being feminized because she is not known to be involved; Because it is of little use in names, by being an actor or a beginner, and in all other circumstances, a memo that if T had not followed it in miniaturization, it was not known to be feminine, and this led to its confusion with the masculine, which most scholars have mentioned, such as Al-Mubarid, Abd Al-Ghaffar Al-Farsi, Al-Sarafi, Ibn Jeni, Abd Al-Qahir Al-Jurjani, and Sheik Abdul Al-Warith, Ibn Sa'un, Bari, Ibn

Khruf, and others (Abd Al-Qahir Al-Jurjani, 2007 : 1/583). Ibn Asfour denied this illness and called it invalid, explaining: "This is what they went to, and it might teach their feminization with their own conscience. You would not mind if they did not see that the reminder was told in Qadam, which is inferred from the return of the male's conscience. The poet said (Al-Qaisi, 1987): 1/519:(

You're his father's wife It's bad for a doggy dog

He will not be removed from it, but he will visit him The forgery of those who blamed you is miserable

Just as he was reminded of the memory of the conscience, why should he not be feminized?"(Ibn Asfour, 2015: 1/85.(

Third problem: Abu Ali Al-Farsi went on to say that inflicting small amounts of shallowness (feet) and "behind" is an anomaly compared to how it should be used for plenty; Because the feminine name, if quaternized, is not followed by the T in miniaturization, toward: scorpion, scorpion, and origin (scorpion); Because the extra letter on the three, although originally in T position, punished it, but those words were reduced to T; Because it came of the rejected origin, as stated in (Al-Aqsa), and in any case it is an rejected origin that is abnormal, cannot be measured. His master's son, Abdul-Qafer Al-Jurjani, Ibn Ya'non, Abu-Barakat Al-Anbari, Al-Qaisi, and Al-Akbari followed in this relationship (Al-Akbari, 2020: 1/441). Ibn Asfour agreed with them on the cause of causing a frost to be attached to miniaturization in these circumstances, which he did in speaking at the advanced poetry house, explaining: "They are oddly affected by the feminization of some sort of miniaturization of three letters, and they followed him to a fold, warning that the original would have been brought to him. Had they not substituted the extra letter for the three letters, can't you see that he said in miniature (feet), which is an addition to three letters: (old); Go back to the rejected original"(Ibn Asfour, 2015, 1/85). She was followed by Ibn Malik and Al-Radi (Ibn Malik, 1982:4/1914.(

What is strange about this illness is that the son of a bird contradicted himself and was disturbed by his rejection of the causes of these scientists, because after he canceled their diseases, he followed them in his book (explaining the glass camel) and took it from the fact that the malfunction in inflicting the feminine syndrome is in minimizing these circumstances; to indicate her femininity, that is: If it were not for the increased pangs, the male would be confused. "A person who acts a little may only be reduced to a necessity because he has heard, and his measurement of miniaturization is the same as the measurement of names. However, you are more than three letters after the feminization of his feminine behavior, because, where his dismissal had no indication of femininity other than the departed names, reporting and referring to them indicate their femininity; So it was said in miniature (front) and (behind): "ancient" and "primitive," for if the feminine T had just followed them, they would have been mentioned"(Ibn Asfour, 1998: 449. Ibn Asfour contradicted himself in his book (Al-Muqrabah) and contradicted what he said in (Al-Moftah), explaining: "They said in (behind): (pneumonia); Because it doesn't go away, if the frost doesn't follow it; They just thought the name was male... They said: (ancient) in miniature (ancient); For the cause advanced in: Behind"(Son of a Bird, 1998: 477). Knowing the causes of the infliction of these conditions, it seems to me that the preponderant cause is to attach them; Lest the masculine woman be confused, and there is no way of knowing the femininity of these conditions except by inflicting them. And as for what the son of a bird did to him in his restoration; Because he knows how to feminize it by restoring her conscience; For the conscience is standing in the place of appearance, for it is in its own wisdom, and its ever-present rulership here, and its successor the rule of conscience (Ibn Al-Hajib, 2014: 1/366.(

Second: The reason for making Jordan a part of "I do" is like a swarm, and not a part of "Seba".

The son of Asfour reasoned as the poet sang (Al-Ajah, 1971: 1/205:(

My heart was in Jordan yesterday

Ibn Asfour came to him, indicating the Ulema leave in Jordan to be from the "swarm" gate, or from the "seba" gate. Each of them said as follows: The first one: Abu Ali Al-Farsi went on to say that the whisper in (Jordan) is superfluous, being like the swarm and others. In this statement, Ibn Sa'un and Ibn Barri (Abu Ali Al-Farsi, 1987: 357). Abu Ali Al-Farsi justified this by saying that the original advantage in shaking her was that of measuring; For if the handshake catches the daughters of (the three), it is to be judged by their increase (Abu Ali Al-Farsi, 1987: (357) The son of Asfour followed up in this statement and in the same illness, saying: "Abu Ali Hamza (Jordan) was made redundant. For if the murmurs follow the daughters of three, they are to be judged as "drowning," in order to show the meaning of their graduation. Their weight (I do) is as "swarm," and "as (I hope)" (Ibn Asfour, 2015: 2/375.(

Second saying: Abu Ali also went on to say that (Jordan) is like (The Album); Yes: I made the weighing of the door a reason. This was followed by Ibn Sa'un and Ibn Barri (Ibn Ya'un, 2008: 1194). Abu Ali did not mention the reason for his vacation, as was the case in the first statement. Ibn Asfour further commented on this saying: "It is also permissible for (Jordan) to be at home like (Al-Ablam), and to place the heavy lifting on the door of (Sabba) and (Kulkul); It is as if the person who justified this by using it in speech is diluted"(Ibn Asfour, 2015: 2 / 375.(

After the son of Asfour presented the sayings of the scholars and the ills contained therein, the first prevailed over the second, and he justified this by saying: "I have the right first face; Because his use of words is more

intense, but some of them lighten it. If his emphasis is proven, he should not be held in the house as a reason; Because this is a necessity that should only be committed if there is no Manduha" (Ibn Asfour, 2015: 2/375). It is understood from this ailment that necessity is in the hands of a bird's son, which cannot be expressed, and can only be committed if the poet does not find the time to speak to another, and therefore he has disagreed with the audience and agreed with Malik's son in the concept of necessity (Al-Siouti, 2006:34.)

Usfur's son contradicted himself by mentioning the problem; Because he mentioned in other than this place in his books (the key) as well, and (the harms of poetry) that poetry is permitted in what is not permitted in speech, whether the poet has it or not, that is: Whether a poet can come up with another, or not, he can say in deed: "I know that poetry, when it was balanced speech, is produced by excess and imperfection of weight health, and is replaced by poetry. Arabs have allowed something that is not permissible in speech, and they were forced to or were not forced to do so; Because it is a place where taxes are familiar" (Ibn Asfour, 1980:13). From the foregoing, it appears that he agreed with the public on the concept of necessity, that a poet may not have a prose, whether compelled or not to do so (Al-Alusi, 1922: 6. After knowing the words of the scholars and their reasoning therein, it seems to me that the first statement that "Jordan" as a source of "swarm" is the most successful among them, for two reasons:

First problem: To say that they are mitigated is necessary, and to say that they are too strict is not necessary; Because it has been proved that he is too strict in speech, and what does not lead to necessity is more than what leads to it. (Al-Seyoti, 1987 : 2/95, 202.)

Second problem: It's much more of a blunt use of speech than a blunt use, and more of a trivial burden than less. Conclusion and search results: Praise be to Allah, prayer, and peace upon His Messenger. And yet, through studying these ills, I have reached results, the most important of which are:

.1The skill of Ibn Asfour, which is based on judgment-oriented by his use of reasoning based on scientific debate based on philosophy, controversy and strong disagreement among scientists, which moves away from educational to complex, and many of his banking judgments meet in more than one cause.

-2The study proved that Ibn Asfour has many contradictory ailments, whether this contradicts his ailments in the book "The Key" and his other works, such as "Explaining the Beautiful to the Glass", "The Teller", "The Teller with the Companion", and "The Harms of Poetry". Or it's contradictory at different places in the key.

.3The son of a bird was attributing some ailments to other scholars and I did not find these ailments, or find their opposite in their printed works.

-4The study established that the derivative at the son of a bird is a means of identifying the original letter of the excess in the Arabic structure.

.5The principle of authenticity is associated with the principle of few and many, as in the increase in whisper, not the first in Nideles, although it is a little broader than Bab Abt and Sater.

.6The reason given by the son of a bird is mostly interpretative, and his concern to review possible cases of the banking issues he deals with, in order to arrive at the morphological truth, has led to a high presumption.

References

- Asrar Al-Arabiya, Abdul Rahman bin Mohammed bin Obaidullah Al-Ansari, Abu Al-Barakat, Kamal Al-Din Al-Anbari (: Publisher: Dar al-Arqam ibn Abi al-Arqam, edition: Jumada I 1, 1420 AH-1999.
- Assimilations and Isotopes in the Way, Jalal Al-Din Al-Seweiti(t911H), Realization of: Group of Investigators, Arabic Language Academy, Damascus, 1407H-1987
- The proposal in the Origins of Grammar, by Imam Jalal Al-Din Al-Siweiti (T911H), seized and commented on: Abdul Hakim Atiyyah, review it and offer it: Aladdin Attia, publisher: Dar Al-Berouti-Damascus, edition: Second, 1427-2006.
- Clarification of evidence: Abi Ali al-Hassan ibn Abdullah al-Qaisi (T6H): Dr. Mohammed Bin Hamoud Al-Dajani, publisher: Dar Al-Gharb Al-Islami - Beirut, edition: I, 1408 E-1987.
- Supplement, by Abi Ali Al-Hassan Bin Ahmed Bin Abd Al-Ghaffar Al-Farsi Al-Nahawi (P.377H), Investigation and study: Dr. Kazim Bahr Al Marjan, publisher: World of Books - Beirut, 2nd edition, 1419 AH-1999 AD.
- Refining the language. Mohammed Bin Ahmed Bin Al-Azhari Al-Harwi, Abu Mansour (P370H). Mohamed Awad Merheb, publisher: Dar Al-Ittihad Al-Arabi-Beirut Edition: I, 2001.
- Dhiwan Aashiq Hamdan, investigation: Dr. Hassan Issa Abu Yassin, publisher: Dar al-Ulum Riyadh, edition: I, 1403, 1983.
- The Great Lovers' Office, Maimoun Bin Qais, commentary and commentary: Dr. Mohamed Hussein, publisher: Literature Library—Model Press.
- Diwan al-Shamekh bin Dharar al-Dhubaiyani: Salah Eddin Al-Hadi, publisher: Egyptian House of Acquaintances.
- Al-Ajaj Court, a novel by Abdul Malik bin Qurayb Al-Asmai, with his explanation: Dr. Abdel Hafiz Al-Satli, publisher: Atlas Library, Damascus, 1971.

- Diwan Al-Qatami, Umair bin Shaim bin Amr bin Abbad Al-Taghlibi (T101H). Investigation and study: Mahmoud al-Rubaie, publisher: Egyptian General Book Organization, edition: I, 2001.
- cupboard. He explained: Al-Alam Al-Shintmari, investigation: Lotfi Al-Saqqal, Al-Khatib's wife, see him: Dr. Fakhreddine Qabawah, publisher: The Arab Book House, Aleppo, Al-Edition: Jumada I 1, 1389 at 1969.
- The secret of the express industry: Father of Al-Fatah Othman Bin Jenni Al-Mosuli (deceased: 392h), investigation: Dr. Hassan Hendawi, publisher: Beirut-Lebanon Science Textbook Publishing House: Jumada al-Oula 1421H 2000.
- Explanation of the discharge. For Al-Qasim's father, Omar Bin Thabet Al-Theni (T442H). Investigation: Dr. Ibrahim bin Sulaiman Al Boaimi, publisher: Al-Rashid Library - Riyadh, edition: Jumada I 1, 1419 BC-1999.
- Al-Kafiya Al-Shafiyya explained to Gamal Al-Din Abu Abdullah Mohammed Bin Abdullah Bin Malik Al-Tai Al-Jayani his achievements and presented to him: Abdel Moneim Ahmed Haridi, publisher: Umm Al-Qura University Center for Scientific Research and Revival of Islamic Heritage Faculty of Sharia and Islamic Studies Mecca, edition: I, 1402 E-1982.
- Explanation of Abu Ali Al-Farsi's Supplement to Halaib Al-Din Abi Al-Qa'd, Abdullah Bin Al-Hussein Al-Akbari (T616H), An Investigation: Dr. Fawziya bint Dalal Al-Otaibi, Dr. Houriya bint Mufrij al-Juhaini, publisher: Al-Rashid Library, Riyadh, first edition, 1442 AH 2020.
- The glass camel explained to Abi Al-Hassan Ali Moemen Bin Mohamed Bin Ali Ibn Asfour Al-Ashbili (669 A.H.), he presented to him and put his margins and indexes: Fawaz al-Shaar: Dr. Emil Badie Yacoub, publisher: Dar al-Kutub al-Alamiya, Beirut, Lebanon: I, 1419-1998.
- Shafiyya Ibn al-Hajeb, Hasan Bin Muhammad Bin Sharaf Shah al-Hussaini al-Astrabadi, Rukn al-Din (T715H), explained an investigation: Dr. Abdel Maqsoud Mohamed Abdel Maqsoud, publisher: Library of Religious Culture, edition: I, 1425 E-2004.
- Shafia Ibn al-Hajeb, Mohammed Bin Al-Hassan Al-Radi Al-Istrabadi, Najmuddin (T686H), explained the following: Mohamed Nour El Hassan, Mohamed Zefzaf and Mohamed Mohieddin Abdel Hamid, publisher: Dar al-Kutub al-Alamiya, Beirut, Lebanon, 1395 AH-1975.
- The clarification evidence explained to Abdullah Bin Berri, An Inquiry: Dr. Eid Mustafa Darwish, publisher: General Authority for Printing Princess Affairs, Cairo, 1405 A.H.-1985.
- Al-Saha is the crown of language and authenticity of Arabic, an investigation: Abu Nasr Ismail Bin Hamad Al-Jawhari Al-Farabi (T393H). Ahmed Abdul Ghafour Attar, publisher: Dar Al-Alam Al-Malaeen - Beirut, edition: the fourth, 1407 A.H.-1987 A.D.
- The Elite at the Millennium Summit, Al-Din Ibrahim bin Al-Hussein, known as the Nile, achieved: Dr. Mohsen Ben Salem Al-Amiri, publisher: Umm al-Qura University, Institute of Scientific Research, Mecca, 1419 A.H.
- Poetry, Ali bin Mu'min bin Muhammad, Al-Hadrami Al-Ishbeli, Abu Al-Hasan known as Ibn Asfour (P669H), investigation: Mr. Ibrahim Mohamed, publisher: Al-Andalus Printing, Publishing and Distribution House, edition: I, 1980.
- The taxes and the pretexts of the poet, without the yoke, Mr. Mahmoud Shukri Al-Alousi, explained: Mohamed Bahjat Azadi, publisher: Arab Library-Baghdad, and Salafi Press-Egypt, 1341H-1922.
- Al-Kitab, by Amro Bin Othman Bin Qanbar Al-Harithi with Loyalty, Abu Bishr, alias Sibuyah (T180H), Investigation: Abdul Salam Mohammed Haroun, publisher: Al-Khanji Library - Cairo, edition: Safar 3, 1408 at 14:88 pm.
- Al-Bab, in the Rationale of Construction and Expression, by the remaining father, Abdullah bin Al-Hussein bin Abdullah Al-Akbari, Al-Baghdadi, Muhabat Al-Din (T616H), Investigation: Dr. Abdulelah Al-Nabhan, publisher: Dar al-Fikr - Damascus, edition: Jumada I 1, 1416 at 1995.
- Not in the words of the Arabs, to Hussein bin Ahmed bin Khalawi, Abu Abdullah (P370H): Achieve: Ahmed Abdel Ghafour Attar, Al-Sabaa: Second, Mecca, 1399 AH-1979 AD.
- What is being spent and what is not going to be spent. For Father Isaac Glass (P311H), an investigation: Huda Mahmoud Qaraqah, publisher: Supreme Council for Islamic Affairs, Committee for the Revival of the Islamic Heritage - Cairo, first edition, 1393H-1971.
- The Ulema Councils, by Abd Al-Rahman Bin Ishaq Al-Baghdadi Al-Nahundi Al-Zaji, Abu Al-Qasim (T337h), achieved: Abdul Salam Mohammed Haroun, publisher: Al Khanji Library, Cairo, Dar Al Rifai, Riyadh, edition: the second 1403 A.H.-1983 A.D.
- The healing group in the science of drainage and calligraphy. It includes on board the healing board of the son of the eyebrow and five explanations for it: He explained the healing to Garbrady (C: 746h), Click Carr (C: 776H) and a footnote on the explanation of Al-Jarbadi to the son of the group (T: 819H) and the adequate curriculum in the explanation of transparency to Zakaria Al-Ansari (T: 926h), and the outstanding benefits of explaining the beautiful tributes to Abraham the Carmiyani (C:1016h), control and care for them: Mohamed Abdel Salam Chahine, publisher: Dar al-Kutub al-Alamiya, Beirut, 1435 AD 2014.

- Calculated in identifying and clarifying the faces of homosexual readers, to Father of the Pioneer Othman Bin Jenni Al-Mosuli (C392H), publisher: Ministry of Endowments-Supreme Council for Islamic Affairs, edition: 1420H-1999
- The male and female summary, by Fadl Bin Salama (T:300H), of his rights, and presented to him and commented on it: Dr. Ramadan Abdel Tawab, publisher: Al-Amir Ghazi's Qur'anic Thought Mural, quoted from Al-Hayat: Institute of Arabic Manuscripts, vol. 17, part two.
- Ad Hoc Committee for the Father of Hassan Ali Bin Ismail Bin Saidah Al-Mursi (T458H), Investigation: Khalil Ibrahim Jafal, publisher: Dar Al-Ittihad Al-Arabi - Beirut, Al-Edition: Jumada I 1, 1417 at 1996.
- Male and female, Abi Bakr: Mohammed Bin Al-Qasim Bin Mohammed Bin Bashar Bin Al-Hassan Bin Bayan Bin Samaah Bin Farwa Bin Qatan Bin Daama Al-Anbari (T: 328e), investigating: Mohamed Abd El-Khaleq Adima, review: Dr. Ramadan Abdel Tawab, publisher: Arab Republic of Egypt - Ministry of Endowments - Supreme Council for Islamic Affairs - Heritage Revival Committee, 1401H-1981.
- Masculine and Feminine, by Abu Hatem Sahl bin Mohammed Al-Sajistani (T255H), investigation: Dr. Hatem Saleh Al Dhamen, publisher: Dar Al-Fikr-Damascus Edition: Jumada I 1, 1418 at 1997.
- Masculine and Feminine, by the father of Zechariah; 207h), achieved it and presented it to him and commented on it: Dr. Ramadan Abdel Tawab, publisher: Cairo Heritage House Library.
- Issues of Halabiya, Abi Ali Al-Farsi (P377H). Achieving: Dr. Hassan Hendawi, publisher: Dar Al-Qalam Printing, Publishing and Distribution, Damascus - Dar Al-Manara Printing, Publishing and Distribution, Beirut, Al-Edition: I, 1407-1987.
- The lamp, for the vaguest evidence yet to be clarified, tells the father of pilgrims, Youssef Ben Yaghb Ben Yeshiva, An investigation has been launched: Dr. Mohammed Bin Hamoud Al-Dajani, publisher: Dean of Scientific Research at the Islamic University of Saudi Arabia, first edition, 1429H-2008.
- The dictionary detailed in the Arabic way: Dear Val Babbiti, publisher: Beirut Scientific Library, first edition, 1413-1992.
- The key in explaining the explanations is to study and investigate the following: Rafi Bin Ghazi Bin Nafie Al-Salmi, publisher: King Faisal Center, first edition, 1436 A.D. 2015.
- Detailed in the Expression Industry, by Abi Al-Qasim Mahmoud Bin Amr Bin Ahmed, Al-Zamkhashri Jar Allah (T538H), An Investigation: Dr. Ali Bou Melhem, publisher: Al-Hilal Library - Beirut, edition: I, 1993.
- Al-Muqtadla, Abdel Qader Al-Jerjani (T471H), Tahqiq: Dr. Ahmed bin Abdullah bin Ibrahim Al Duwaish, publisher: Dean of Scientific Research at Imam Muhammad Bin Saud Islamic University, Saudi Arabia, first edition, 1428H-2007.
- Abul Abbas Muhammad Bin Yazid Al Mubarid (T285H), Investigation: Mohamed Abdelkhaleq Azima, publisher: the world of books. - Beirut.
- The close person, along with a representative of the close relative, to Abi Al-Hasan Ali bin Mohammed bin Ali bin Asfour Al-Hadrami Al-Ashbili (T669H), investigation, commentary, and study: Adel Ahmed Abdul Majud, and Ali Mohammed Mouawad, publisher: Beirut Lebanon Science Textbook Publishing House: Jumada I 1, 1418 at 1998.

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